

central ring). On complexation, the multiple splittings of these two bands arise from out-of-plane motions other than those in phase and also probably from overtones of low lying fundamentals in resonance. The splitting of these two bands appears to be metal sensitive.

These facts suggest a coordination of the alkali metals with 1,10-phenanthroline through the nitrogen atoms of its pyridine fragments.

The ir spectra of these adducts point to the absence of hydrogen bonding in them, showing thereby that hydrogen bonding between a chelating ligand and the alkali metal salt of a chelate anion is not necessary for formation of the adducts.

Conductivities :

Molar conductivities of all the adducts were measured in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone at 25° at a concentration of 10⁻³ M. The solvent was calibrated by Banerjee *et al*⁵ and they observed that the values of molar conductivities in the range 35-40 cm⁻¹ correspond to 1 : 1 electrolyte.

It is observed from the results that none of the values approach either ideal or 1 : 1 electrolyte. Low values of molar conductivities of these adducts seem to indicate neutral complexes. The trend Li < Na < K would indicate that the lithium complex is the strongest in solution.

Probable structure :

The above discussion suggests the coordination of the ligand 1,10-phenanthroline with alkali metals through nitrogen atoms of the pyridine fragments. Accordingly, these adducts should have the following structure :

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Metal Derivatives of Organo-Antimony Compounds : Reactions of Anhydrous Chlorides of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with Arylantimony Compounds

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IN continuation of our study on the reactions between arylantimony compounds and anhydrous metal chlorides¹⁻³, we report here the reactions of manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) chlorides with tetraphenylstibonium chloride.

Experimental

The hydrated metal chlorides (B.D.H. or Sarabhai Chemicals) were dehydrated⁴ by refluxing them with thionyl chloride and the anhydrous metal chlorides thus obtained were used after analyses. Triphenylstibine was prepared by Wurtz reaction from antimony trichloride, benzene and sodium metal⁵. Tetraphenylstibonium chloride was prepared by the known method⁶. Solvents were dried and deoxygenated before use. Because of the hygroscopic nature of some of the reactants, all preparations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Dry nitrogen gas was flushed into the reaction mixture to maintain an inert atmosphere.

Preparation of quaternary stibonium complexes : A general method was employed for preparing the quaternary stibonium complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) chlorides using the stoichiometric amounts of the reactants.

To a dry alcoholic or acetonitrile solution of anhydrous metal chloride was added slowly and dropwise, a solution of tetraphenylstibonium chloride in benzene or alcohol under dry nitrogen atmosphere with constant shaking at room temperature. No heat evolved during the mixing of the reactants. Nitrogen gas was passed for 5 to 10 hr with occasional shaking. The solution was concentrated by evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure. The flask was stoppered and kept aside when solid compound started depositing slowly. The supernatant was decanted into another flask after keeping the reaction mixture for a day or two. The compound was washed with dry benzene (2-3 times) and finally with *n*-hexane. It was then dried *in vacuo* (1-2 mm) for 2 hr. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Reaction of anhydrous copper(II) chloride with triphenylstibine : To a dry benzene solution of anhydrous cupric chloride was added benzene solution of triphenylstibine slowly and with constant stirring under dry nitrogen atmosphere. After 20-24 hr, a white solid started depositing which was found

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTIVITY AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	m.p. °C	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)		Molar conductance in DMF (mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹)	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Metal	Chloride		
[Ph ₄ Sb] ₂ [MnCl ₄]	Light pink	215	5.06 (5.20)	13.81 (13.45)	89.66	5.89
[Ph ₄ Sb] ₂ [CoCl ₄]	Greenish-blue	248(d)	5.86 (5.55)	14.29 (13.40)	115.06	4.28
[Ph ₄ Sb] ₂ [NiCl ₄]	Light yellow	140	6.21 (5.53)	13.69 (13.39)	111.76	3.62
[Ph ₄ Sb] ₂ [CuCl ₄]	Reddish-brown	205	5.48 (5.96)	13.52 (13.34)	103.63 (40.89)*	1.98
[Ph ₄ Sb] ₂ [ZnCl ₄]	White	250(d)	6.58 (6.12)	14.24 (13.32)	95.25 (38.60)*	Diamagnetic

d = Decomposed ; * Molar conductivity in nitrobenzene at 30°.

to be Cu₂Cl₂. The solid was filtered, washed with dry benzene and triphenylantimony dichloride was obtained from the filtrate on evaporation of the solvent and recrystallization of the crude product, m.p. 142° (lit. m.p. 143°).

Reaction of anhydrous zinc(II) chloride with triphenylstibine: A mixture of an alcoholic solution of zinc(II) chloride and benzene solution of triphenylstibine, on refluxing for 4 hr and then evaporating the solvent to 3/4 of its volume under reduced pressure, gave a white solid compound which was filtered and dried *in vacuo* (1-2 mm) at room temperature, m.p. 53-55° (lit. m.p. for Ph₂SbCl 53-57°). Solvent from the filtrate was also removed under reduced pressure (1-2 mm).

Physical measurements :

Infrared spectra of the compounds (4000-600 cm⁻¹) were taken in nujol on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Far ir spectra (600-250 cm⁻¹) were taken using polythene sheets. PMR spectrum was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrophotometer in DMSO-d₆. The chemical shifts are expressed in δ (ppm). The conductivity measurements were carried out in dimethylformamide on an Elico conductivity bridge, type CM-82T. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on Guoy's balance.

Results and Discussion

The compounds obtained from the different metal chlorides and tetraphenylstibonium chloride were solid, having light pink colour for manganese, bluish green for cobalt, light yellow for nickel, reddish brown for copper and white crystalline for zinc complexes, respectively. Their melting points are given in Table 1. The compounds were insoluble in most common organic solvents except dimethylformamide, acetonitrile, dimethylsulphoxide and nitrobenzene.

The analytical data (Table 1) of the quaternary stibonium complexes indicate the formation of [Ph₄Sb]₂[MCl₄] [M = Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) or Zn(II)] from tetraphenylstibonium chloride and anhydrous metal chlorides, when reacted in 2 : 1 molar ratio.

The conductivity measurements indicate the formation of ionic complexes. The molar conductance values (89.66-115.06 mhos cm² mole⁻¹) (Table 1) indicated uni-bivalent electrolytic behaviour for the quaternary stibonium complexes.

The infrared spectra of the tetraphenylstibonium cation, [Ph₄Sb]⁺, showed bands of medium intensity in the region 440-430 cm⁻¹ which could be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sb-C(Ph)}}$ vibrations⁷. Since only one band was observed due to carbon-antimony asymmetric stretching frequency, it could be inferred that all the bonds are equivalent and the cation has T_d symmetry.

A regular tetrahedral anion, [MCl₄]⁻, has only two infrared active fundamentals ν_3 and ν_4 and these are triply degenerate. The bands due to ν_3 vibrations for tetrachlorometallate ions, [MnCl₄]²⁻, [CoCl₄]²⁻, [NiCl₄]²⁻, [CuCl₄]²⁻ and [ZnCl₄]²⁻ were observed at 290, 295, 290, 275 and 215 cm⁻¹, respectively which are in agreement with the results reported for these anions by Clark⁸, Adam⁹ and Sabatini¹⁰. In case of [CuCl₄]²⁻ anion, a weak band at 265 cm⁻¹ was observed which is suggestive of distorted tetrahedral symmetry.

The magnetic moment of [MnCl₄]²⁻ anion (5.89 B.M.) is in the range of tetrahedral complexes of manganese as has been reported for [Ph₄M]₂[MnCl₄] complexes (M = N, P, or As)¹¹⁻¹³. The magnetic moment of [Ph₄Sb]₂[CoCl₄] has been found to be 4.28 B.M. which is comparable to the magnetic moments of the tetrahedral [CoCl₄]²⁻ anion in Cs₂CoCl₄ (4.71 B.M.). The magnetic susceptibility of tetrahedral tetrahalo-nickel complexes have been reported to be in the range of 3.6-4.0 B.M., e.g., 3.89 B.M. for [(C₂H₅)₄N]₂[NiCl₄]¹⁴. The observed value of 3.62 B.M. for [Ph₄Sb]₂[NiCl₄] is comparable to the reported value. The value of 1.98 B.M. for [CuCl₄]²⁻ anion in [(Ph₄Sb)]₂[CuCl₄] supported the view that there is deviation from regular tetrahedral arrangement in copper complex because a perfect tetrahedral tetrahalo complex has a relatively large orbital contribution leading to the effective magnetic moment of 2.2 B.M.¹¹. The stibonium complex of tetrachlorozinc(II) was found to be diamagnetic as expected for d¹⁰ system.

The pmr spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_4\text{Sb}]_2[\text{NiCl}_4]$ in DMSO-d_6 showed complex multiplets in the range δ 7.47-7.90 which were attributed to the aromatic protons.

Attempts were made to synthesize the complexes of anhydrous metal chlorides with triphenylantimony dichloride. However, these reactions were unsuccessful probably because of the lower stability of C-Sb bond compared to C-P or C-As bond.

Triphenylstibine reduced copper(II) chloride to copper(I) chloride, when reacted in 1:2 molar ratio under dry nitrogen atmosphere and itself was converted into the corresponding dichloride. Similar reduction products have been reported by other workers^{15,16} also. However, when triphenylstibine was reacted with anhydrous zinc(II) chloride, a metathetic reaction occurred between the two, cleaving the C-Sb bond with the formation of Ph_3SbCl and PhZnCl . This can be represented as $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb} + \text{ZnCl}_2 \rightarrow \text{Ph}_2\text{SbCl} + \text{PhZnCl}$. The products, though not obtained in very pure state, were confirmed by elemental analyses and melting point data. Such a cleavage of C-Sb bond by mercury and some other metal compounds have also been reported earlier¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

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Studies on the Metal Chelates of 8-Hydroxy-quinolino-5-(*p*-Tolyl)sulphonamide as Potential Drugs

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THE chemistry of quinoline and *p*-toluene sulphonamides has attracted special attention because of their therapeutic properties^{1,2}. Some of the sulphonamides are used in the treatment of cancer³, tuberculosis⁴, diabetes⁵, malaria⁶, leprosy⁷ and convulsion⁸. They are also active against different types of bacteria. It has recently been observed that some drugs have increased activity when administered as metal complexes, 'more so as their metal chelates'^{9,10}. A similar mechanism was also observed in our previous study¹¹⁻¹³. In continuation of the previous work and to test the change in antibacterial activity of ligands on chelation, we report here the synthesis of metal chelates of 8-hydroxyquinolino-5-(*p*-tolyl)sulphonamide [HQTS] with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) metals.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and recrystallized. The metal-ligand ratio was determined by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation. IR spectra were recorded on an automatic Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in KBr phase. Metals were estimated by standard methods¹⁴, sulphur by modified Messenger's method¹⁵ and nitrogen by modified Kjeldahl's method¹⁶.

The ligand HQTS was prepared by the general method¹² by taking 8-hydroxyquinoline as the starting material. The ligand was dissolved in warm distilled water. 0.1 M solution of the ligand was treated with 0.1 M aqueous solution of the metal salts at 50-60°. The pH was maintained between 8-9 by using borate buffer. The resulting precipitates of the chelates were digested on a water bath for 30 min, filtered, washed and recrystallized.

IR spectra : A broad distinct band at 2900 cm^{-1} was found in the spectrum of HQTS. This value is less than the prescribed limit (3700-3300 cm^{-1}) for -OH group and is due to hydrogen bonding^{17,18}. On this basis the intramolecular hydrogen bonded chelate structure (-O-H-N) was proposed for

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